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STANDARDS-BASED VALUE CREATION FOR MODERN WASTE-TO-ENERGY FACILITIES

*Vesna Alivojvodić¹, The Academy of Applied Studies Polytechnic
Niko Samec², Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Maribor
Filip Kokalj³, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Maribor*

Abstract: *This paper examines the integration of ISO 59010 circular economy principles into Waste-to-Energy (WtE) plant operations to enhance the implementation of Best Available Techniques Conclusions (BATC) under the EU Industrial Emissions Directive (IED). WtE facilities face increasing pressure to move beyond compliance toward holistic circular performance. The paper identifies synergies between regulatory BATC requirements, which focus on emissions, monitoring, and energy efficiency, and the business model transition framework, which emphasizes systemic value creation, resource optimization, and collaboration within value networks. By aligning monitoring and performance metrics through indicators focused on circularity, plants can shift from linear waste processing systems to circular energy and material recovery hubs. The proposed integration model introduces a three-level approach that connects circular economy principles with operational BATC implementation through practical self-monitoring and inspection tools. This approach supports improved transparency, reduced environmental impact, and measurable economic benefits. The research provides a conceptual and applied framework for policy development and strategic decision-making in circular economy transitions within the WtE sector.*

Keywords: Waste-to-Energy (WtE) Plant, ISO 59010, Best Available Techniques Conclusions (BATC), Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), Circular Economy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Contemporary waste management challenges in Europe require a transformative approach that moves beyond traditional linear models toward circular economic systems. Through its Industrial Emissions Directive (IED) [1] and Best Available Techniques (BAT) reference documents [2], the European Union has set ambitious goals to reduce environmental impact and promote changes in how organizations create, deliver, and retain value, as outlined in the European Green Deal and Circular Economy Action Plan [3, 4]. Waste-to-Energy (WtE) facilities are a key component of the European waste management strategy, enabling energy recovery and reducing reliance on landfills [5]. However, traditional WtE plant operations remain primarily focused on achieving regulatory compliance through the implementation of Best Available Techniques Conclusions (BATC), without systematically considering opportunities to create additional value through circular economy principles. The implementation of 37 individual BATC [6] for the waste incineration sector presents significant operational challenges. Current BATC requirements mandate comprehensive self-monitoring plans covering emissions to air and water, waste management, and energy efficiency, with continuous monitoring of over 30 parameters [6]. Even when ensuring environmental protection levels, these requirements are often perceived as compliance burdens rather than opportunities for

¹valivojvodic@politehnika.edu.rs

²niko.samec@um.si

³filip.kokalj@um.si

operational optimization. The fragmented BATC implementation approach treats each requirement in isolation, missing potential synergies and failing to integrate circular economy perspectives.

The ISO 59010:2024 Circular Economy – Guidance on the Transition of Business Models and Value Networks standard provides a business-oriented methodology for implementing circular principles into organizational strategy [7]. Analysis of IMPEL practical tools [3] and systemic value creation methodology reveals significant integration opportunities. Key convergence areas include synchronization of monitoring systems, expansion of value networks through industrial symbiosis, and optimization of residue management. In this way, compliance requirements can be transformed into revenue-generating opportunities. This paper addresses the fundamental question: How can the ISO 59010 framework [7] be integrated into WtE plant operations to enhance BAT implementation [6] and create additional value through circular value networks? The research develops a framework enabling WtE operators to transform regulatory requirements from compliance burdens into value creation opportunities, implement measurable circular key performance indicators (KPIs) [5] to complement existing BATC monitoring systems, and establish value networks that enable industrial symbiosis and innovative business models.

2. BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

2.1 Regulatory Context

The BATC for Waste Incineration establishes a comprehensive regulatory framework with 37 individual conclusions organized into eight major categories: environmental management systems, monitoring, general environmental performance, energy efficiency, air emissions, water emissions, material efficiency, and noise [6]. Published under the EU IED in December 2019, these conclusions set binding minimum standards for WtE facilities across the European Union. Key conclusions for circular economy integration include [6]:

- BAT 1, which mandates Environmental Management Systems with 28 specific features, including monitoring programs, waste stream management, and residue management plans;
- BAT 11, which establishes risk-based waste acceptance procedures, including radioactivity detection and analysis of key parameters such as calorific value and hazardous substance content; and
- BAT 14, which requires combined techniques such as waste blending, advanced control systems, and incineration optimization to improve environmental performance and reduce unburnt substances in bottom ashes.

Annual monitoring costs for typical medium-sized WtE facilities range from 200,000 to 450,000 EUR [8], representing substantial compliance burdens that operators often perceive as purely regulatory rather than value-creating. Despite persistent implementation gaps four years after publication, IMPEL developed practical tools [3] that provide systematic compliance frameworks but do not integrate circular economy perspectives.

2.2 Business Model Standards

The ISO 59010:2024 standard provides a business-oriented methodology for transitioning from linear take-make-dispose systems to circular economic models that maintain resources at their highest value. Building on the value network approach, the standard emphasizes six interconnected core principles [7]: systems thinking, which recognizes interconnections between components and applies holistic decision-making; value creation, which generates economic, environmental, and social benefits relative to resource use and conservation; value sharing, which ensures equitable benefit distribution among stakeholders; resource stewardship, which manages resources efficiently throughout their entire lifecycles; resource traceability, which enables transparent tracking of material flows to support recovery and quality maintenance; and ecosystem resilience, which maintains and enhances ecosystem capacity to provide services while regenerating natural capital.

The standard defines the circular economy as an economic system that uses systematic approaches to maintain circular resource flows by recovering, retaining, or adding to their value while contributing to sustainable development. It establishes value creation models as interconnected organizational decisions that determine how organizations create, deliver, and capture value across temporal horizons. The ISO 59010 standard structures the transition to a circular economy through ten basic business model elements [7]: value proposition, key activities, resources, customer segments, customer relationships, channels, costs, revenue streams, key partners, and external elements such as public infrastructure and ecosystem services. Value networks enable industrial symbiosis, which is particularly relevant for WtE plants by connecting with consumers of electrical and thermal energy, producers of building materials, and agricultural producers. The transition process includes eight sequential steps [7]: defining goals, understanding current models, mapping value chains and resource flows, determining boundaries, assessing circularity, considering actions, determining strategy, and establishing monitoring systems.

The convergence between BATC requirements and circular economy principles creates significant integration opportunities. The first area is the synchronization of monitoring systems, where BATC requirements can be aligned with circular performance indicators. Another area is the expansion of value networks through industrial symbiosis, enabling the delivery of electrical and thermal energy, the use of bottom ash in construction, and the generation of compost. The third area is the optimization of waste management, where BATC requirements are transformed into opportunities to generate value through circular business models and the establishment of reverse logistics systems.

3. METHODS

This study uses a literature review and framework synthesis approach to develop an integration model between circular economy principles (ISO 59010:2024) and WtE plant operations under BATC requirements. The research methodology consists of three phases: (1) Regulatory and standards analysis through review of the EU IED [1], BATC for waste incineration [6], and the standard [7]; (2) Gap identification through systematic mapping of BATC compliance requirements against the six core principles to identify integration opportunities; (3) Synthesis of key sources, including IMPEL practical implementation tools [3], ISO circular economy guidance [7], and WtE sector literature [9, 10]. The framework is based on a three-layer integration architecture that connects regulatory compliance with circular value creation and incorporates iterative analysis of synergies between BATC monitoring requirements and circular KPIs.

4. INTEGRATION FRAMEWORK

4.1. Baseline Assessment

Traditional WtE operations use linear models, treating waste as material and energy inputs and residues as disposal outputs. A typical 200,000-ton-per-year facility produces 40,000–50,000 tons of incineration bottom ash, 4,000–6,000 tons of air pollution control residues, and 150–200 GWh of electrical energy annually, achieving only 20–30% electrical energy efficiency with R1 factors of 0.6–0.8 [8, 9]. Metals in bottom ash, valued at 50–100 EUR per ton, remain 60% unexploited [11]. Critical intervention points include pre-treatment optimization through advanced waste characterization to enable material recovery-based selection, combustion optimization using systems thinking to improve efficiency via advanced process control integrating real-time composition data, and post-combustion value stream development through optimized metal recovery and bottom ash applications in construction materials, while establishing industrial symbiosis networks.

4.2 Three-Layer Integration Model

The authors propose a framework that employs a three-layer architecture connecting the six principles with WtE operations and BATC compliance. Layer one implements these principles, operationalized through industrial symbiosis networks that connect WtE plants with steel mills, cement plants, and district heating systems. Layer two transforms WtE operations through smart waste sorting and blending, enhanced combined heat and power production, integrated material recovery, advanced control systems that simultaneously optimize emissions and recovery, and circular product development from residues. Layer three extends BATC monitoring through enhanced self-monitoring that integrates circular KPIs with traditional parameters, advanced emission control using predictive analytics, and systematic inspection evaluating compliance and circular performance. Vertical integration enables bidirectional information flows between layers, while horizontal synergies are optimized through cross-functional teams and stakeholder engagement platforms. The practical application of this three-layer architecture is illustrated by systematically mapping ISO 59010 principles to specific BATC requirements. Table 1 shows how each circular economy principle translates into concrete integration actions within the WtE operational context, linking strategic principles with regulatory compliance elements.

Table 1. Integration of circular economy principles with BATC compliance in WtE operations.

Source: Authors, based on ISO 59010:2024

ISO 59010 principle	WtE operation / BATC compliance element	Integration action
System thinking	Process control / Emission control (BAT 21-31)	Integrated control systems for emission and recovery balance
	Energy recovery / Energy efficiency (BAT 19-20)	CHP* systems with district heating networks
Value creation	Waste input optimization / Self-monitoring plans (BAT 2-8)	Enhanced waste characterization with circular assessment
	Material recovery / Performance KPIs* (BAT 35-36)	Advanced IBA* processing with metal recovery optimization
Value sharing	Stakeholder engagement / EMS* Stakeholder engagement (BAT 1)	Multi-stakeholder platforms for circular value distribution
	Benefit distribution / Reporting (Article 55)	Multi-stakeholder reporting dashboard with quantified value distribution metrics
Resource stewardship	Waste stream management / Waste acceptance (BAT 11)	Risk-based acceptance with circular criteria
	Output quality control / Residue management (BAT 1)	Lifecycle-based residue valorization strategies
Resource traceability	Material flow tracking / Monitoring plans (BAT 2-8)	Digital tracking systems for input-output material flows
	Quality documentation / Material tracking (BAT 14)	Material passports and ISO 14001-based quality tracking for recovered products
Ecosystem resilience	Environmental protection / Emission limits (BAT 21-31)	Carbon capture and utilization technologies
	Carbon management / Energy recovery (BAT 19-20)	Renewable energy integration and ecosystem restoration programs

* IBA = Incineration Bottom Ash; CHP = Combined Heat and Power; KPI = Key Performance Indicator; EMS = Environmental Management System

Implementing this integrated framework requires a phased approach to ensure systematic adoption and measurable progress.

4.3 Implementation Phases and Tools

The proposed model implementation recommendation follows three phases over 24 to 36 months:

- The foundation phase (months 6 to 12) establishes circular economy teams, conducts baseline assessments using the ISO 59020 methodology, develops integration plans with existing environmental management systems, and initiates stakeholder engagement.
- The pilot phase (months 12 to 24) implements enhanced monitoring by tracking circular KPIs alongside BAT parameters, executes material recovery optimization pilots, develops industrial symbiosis partnerships, and delivers training programs.
- The full integration phase (months 24 to 36) achieves complete integration of circular principles into operations, deploys advanced process control systems, establishes functional value networks, and implements standardized reporting protocols.

Implementation tools include circular performance dashboards that integrate BATC monitoring data with circular KPIs, enhanced self-monitoring plans that extend IMPEL templates with circular elements, and risk management frameworks addressing technical, economic, regulatory, and stakeholder risks. Performance tracking uses a multi-level indicator framework structured by priority. Suggested targets are organized into three tiers: Tier 1 – primary operational targets; Tier 2 – economic and compliance metrics; Tier 3 – strategic partnerships, as follows:

- Tier 1 targets an 85% material recovery rate, a 40% reduction in landfilled waste, and a 0.15-point increase in the R1 energy efficiency factor (this R1 increase represents meaningful progress toward achieving the EU energy recovery status threshold) [12].
- Tier 2 targets 30% fewer BREF exceedances, 10–15% operational cost reductions, and 20% additional revenue from circular products.
- Tier 3 establishes a minimum of three industrial symbiosis partnerships and tracks circular research development.

Reporting protocols align with BATC requirements while adding circular perspectives through monthly operational reports, quarterly stakeholder updates, annual sustainability assessments, and regulatory submissions demonstrating enhanced environmental performance.

5. DISCUSSION

The proposed three-layer integration concept differs significantly from conventional approaches to implementing BAT conclusions. By systematically linking ISO 59010 circular economy principles with operational BATC requirements, this framework enables WtE facilities to transform regulatory mandates into value creation opportunities. The framework's primary contribution is its ability to operationalize abstract circular economy principles within the concrete regulatory environment of waste incineration. Previous approaches have often treated BATC compliance and the circular economy transition as separate initiatives. Through this integration model, their mutual reinforcement, circular thinking, and environmental performance can be demonstrated. BATC monitoring infrastructure provides measurement systems for tracking circular outcomes.

The convergence between BATC requirements and the six core principles creates significant integration opportunities. The first area is the synchronization of monitoring systems, where BATC requirements can be aligned with circular performance indicators. Another area is the expansion of value networks through industrial symbiosis, enabling the delivery of thermal energy, the use of ash in construction, and the generation of compost. The third area is the optimization of waste management, where BATC requirements are transformed into pathways for environmental and economic benefits through circular business models and the establishment of reverse logistics systems.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a novel integration framework that connects ISO 59010 circular economy principles with BATC-based WtE operations, addressing a critical gap in current waste management

literature. The proposed three-layer architecture shows how regulatory compliance can become an opportunity for circular value generation through systematic integration of monitoring systems, operational processes, and value network development. The framework has significant practical implications for multiple stakeholders. WtE operators gain a structured approach to improve environmental performance and economic viability. Regulators receive a model for evolving BATC guidance toward circular economy objectives. Policymakers can use this framework to align industrial emissions control with broader circular economy strategies under the European Green Deal. Key recommendations for implementation include: (1) starting with existing BATC monitoring infrastructure and gradually integrating circular KPIs; (2) developing local industrial symbiosis partnerships early in the transition process; (3) adopting a phased approach over 24–36 months to manage investment requirements; and (4) establishing stakeholder engagement protocols to support value network development. As the EU advances toward circular economy transitions, integrating these principles into sector-specific BATC frameworks offers a pragmatic path to regulatory excellence and circular innovation. Future work should focus on empirical validation and extension to other waste management sectors.

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